

BIRINCHI DARAJALI TAQQOSLAMALARNI YECHISH USULLARI.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10673179>

ANNOTATSIYA.

Maqolada taqqoslamalar yechish usullari va usullar asosida birinchi darajali taqqoslash olib boriladi va natijalar chiqarilishi o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Koeffisient, ko'phad, Eyler teoremasi, uzluksiz kasrlar.

ANNOTATION.

Coefficient, polynomial, Euler's theorem, continued fractions.

Taqqoslamalar o'zaro bog'liqlik va taqqoslash usullari bo'yicha har bir sohada o'zgartirib boriladi. Taqqoslashni to'g'ri amalga oshirish uchun, ma'lumotlar olish, tahlil qilish, natijalarni chiqarish lozim. Bu usullar asosida birinchi darajali taqqoslash olib boriladi va natijalar chiqariladi.

Asosiy tushunchalar: bir noma'lumli n - darajali taqqoslama, taqqoslamaning yechimi, teng kuchli taqqoslamalar, bir noma'lumli birinchi darajali taqqoslama, tub modulli taqqoslama.

Koeffisientlari butun sonlardan iborat

$$f(x) = a_0x^n + a_1x^{n-1} + \dots + a_{n-1}x^1 + a_n$$

ko'phad berilgan bo'lsin.

Ushbu $f(x) \equiv 0(\text{mod}m)$ (a_0 son m ga bo'linmaydi, $a_i \in \mathbb{Z}, m \geq 1$) ko'rinishdagi taqqoslamani bir noma'lumli n - darajali taqqoslama deyiladi.

Agar $x = s$ bo'lganda $f(c) \equiv 0(\text{mod}m)$ taqqoslama to'g'ri bo'lsa, u holda c son $f(x)$ taqqoslamani qanoatlantiradi deyiladi.

Agar c son $f(x)$ taqqoslamani qanoatlantirsa, u holda \bar{c} chegirmalar sinfi $f(x)$ taqqoslamaning yechimi deyiladi.

Yechimlari to'plami ustma-ust tushgan taqqoslamalarni teng kuchli taqqoslamalar deyiladi.

Ushbu $ax \equiv b(\text{mod}m)$ ($a, b \in \mathbb{Z}; \forall m \in \mathbb{N}$) ko'rinishdagi taqqoslamaga bir noma'lumli birinchi darajali taqqoslama deyiladi.

Misol. $7 * x \equiv 10(\text{mod}4)$ taqqoslamaning yechimlarini taqqoslama xossaligidan foydalanib toping.

Yechish. $(7,4) = 1$ ekanligidan taqqoslama yagona yechimga ega ekanligi kelib chiqadi. 7 va 11 sonlari 4 dan katta bo'lganligi uchun $7 * x \equiv 3x(\text{mod}4)$ va $10 \equiv 2(\text{mod}4)$ lardan foydalanib

$3x \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ ni hosil qilamiz. Bundan $3x \equiv -x \pmod{4}$ ni e'tiborga olib $-x \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ ni, va nihoyat $x \equiv -2 \pmod{4}$ ni hosil qilamiz.

Agar $-2 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ ni qo'llasak, u holda $x \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ kelib chiqadi.

Tekshirish : $7 * 2 \equiv 10 \pmod{4}$

$$14 \equiv 10 \pmod{4} \Rightarrow (14 - 10) = 4 : 4$$

kelib chiqadi.

Misol. $27x \equiv 47 \pmod{38}$ taqqoslamani taqqoslama xossalaridan foydalanib yechimlarini toping.

Yechish. $47 \equiv 9 \pmod{38}$ dan $27x \equiv 9 \pmod{38}$ hosil bo'ladi. $(27, 38) = 1$

bo'lgani uchun taqqoslama yagona yechimga ega. $(9, 38) = 1$

bo'lgani uchun taqqoslamani ikkala tomonini 9 ga bo'lamiz:

$$3x \equiv 1 \pmod{38}.$$

Taqqoslamani o'ng tomoniga 38 ni qo'shamiz: $3x \equiv 39 \pmod{38}$.

Hosil bo'lgan taqqoslamani ikkala tomonini $(3, 38) = 1$ bo'lgani uchun 3 ga bo'lamiz:

$$x \equiv 3 \pmod{38}.$$

Tekshirish: $27 * 13 - 47 = 304 = (38 * 8) : 38$.

Bir noma'lumli birinchi darajali taqqoslamani yechishning ba'zi usullari bilan tanishib chiqaylik. Faraz qilaylik, bizga $ax \equiv b \pmod{m}$ (1) taqqoslama berilgan bo'lsin.

1. Tanlash usuli (1) taqqoslama bu usul orqali yechish uchun taqqoslamadagi x o'rniga chigirmalarning to'la sistemadagi barcha chigirmalar ketma -ket qo'yib chiqiladi. Ulardan qaysi biri to'g'ri taqqoslamaga aylantirsa, usha yechim bo'lim hisoblanadi. Biz oldingi temadagi ikkita misolni shu usulda yechishdik. Ammo taqqoslama moduli ancha katta bo'lganda bu usul unga samara bermaydi.

2. Koeffitsentlarni o'zlashtirish usuli. Taqqoslamani bu usul orqali yechish uchun taqqoslamalarning xossalaridan foydalanib noma'lum oldidagi koeffitsentni va b ni shunday o'zgartirish kerakki o'ng tomonda hosil bo'lgan son x ning koeffitsentiga bo'linsin.

Agar $(b, m) = d > 0$ bo'lsa, yangi o'zgaruvchiga o'tish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

1. Misollar.

$$7x \equiv 5 \pmod{9}$$

$$7x \equiv (5+9) \pmod{9}$$

$$7x \equiv 14 \pmod{9} \quad (7, 9) = 1 \quad \text{bo'lganidan}$$

$$x \equiv 2 \pmod{9} \quad \text{bo'ladi}$$

$$2. 17x \equiv 25 \pmod{28}$$

$$17x + 28 \equiv 25 \pmod{28}, \quad 45x \equiv 25 \pmod{28},$$

$$9x \equiv 5 \pmod{28}, \quad (9, 28) = 1 \text{ bo'lganidan}$$

$$9x \equiv 5 \pmod{28},$$

$$9x \equiv 5 - 140 \pmod{28} \equiv -135 \pmod{28}$$

$$9x \equiv 135 \pmod{28}$$

$$x \equiv -15 \equiv 13 \pmod{28}$$

3. Eyler teoremasidan foydalanish. Bizga ma'lumki, agar $(a, m) = 1$ bo'lsa u holda $a^{\varphi(m)} \equiv 1 \pmod{m}$ edi.

Buning har ikkala tomonini b ga ko'paytirsak deb yozish mumkin. Oxirgi taqqoslamani $a^{\varphi(m)}b \equiv b \pmod{m}$ bilan solishtirib,

$$x \equiv a^{\varphi(m)-1} \cdot b \pmod{m} \text{ ekanligiga}$$

ishonch hosil qilish mumkin. Ammo misollar yechimida $a^{\varphi(m)-1}b$ ifodani m model bo'yicha eng kichik chegirmaga keltirish lozim.

Misol.

$$3x \equiv 7 \pmod{11}$$

$$x \equiv 3^{\varphi(11)-1} \cdot 7 \pmod{11} \quad \varphi(11) = 10$$

$$3^2 \equiv 9 \equiv -2 \pmod{11} \quad 34 \equiv 4 \pmod{11}$$

$$3^5 \equiv 12 \equiv 1 \pmod{11}; \quad 3^9 \equiv 4 \pmod{11} \text{ bo'lganidan } x \equiv 3^9 \cdot 7 \equiv 28 \equiv 6 \pmod{11} \text{ yoki } x \equiv 6 \pmod{11}$$

Mabodo taqqoslamani moduli yetarlicha katta bo'lsa, yuqoridgi usullarining birortasi ham uncha samara bermaydi. Bunday taqqoslamalarni yechish uchun quyidagi usuldan foydalanamiz.

4. Uzluksiz kasrlardan foydalanish usuli. Bizga quyidagi $ax \equiv b \pmod{m}$ (1)

taqqoslama berilgan bo'lsin, bunda $(a, m) = 1$ va $a > 0$, $\frac{m}{a}$ kasrni uzluksiz kasrga

yoyib, uning sunosib kasrlarini $\frac{P_k}{Q_k} (k = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ deb belgilaymiz. Bu kasr

qisqarmas kasr bo'lganidan $P_n = m, Q_n = a$, u holda $P_n Q_{n-1} - P_{n-1} Q_n = (-1)^n$, tenglik

$m Q_{n-1} - P_{n-1} a = (-1)^n$ shaklini oladi. Bu tenglikdan $a \cdot P_{n-1} = -(-1)^n + m Q_{n-1}$ yoki

$a P_{n-1} \equiv (-1)^{n-1} \pmod{m}$ ni hosil qilamiz. Oxirgi taqqoslamani ikkala tomonini $(-1)^{n-1} b$

ga ko'paytramiz: $a \cdot (-1)^{n-1} \cdot b \cdot P_{n-1} \equiv b \pmod{m}$ (2) Bu oxirgi (2) va (1) formuladan (3)

$x \equiv (-1)^{n-1} \cdot b \cdot P_{n-1} \pmod{m}$ hosil qilamiz. Bunda P_{n-1} son $\frac{m}{a}$ kasrning $(n-1)$ munosib kasrdagi suratdan iborat. Dastlabki (1) taqqoslamani yagona yechimga ega

bo'lgani uchun ham (3) yechim (1) taqqoslamaning yechimi bo'ladi.

Misol. $285x \equiv 177 \pmod{924}$ taqqoslama yechilsin.

$(285, 924) \equiv 3$ va $177 = 3 \cdot 59$ bo'lgani sababli taqqoslamaning moduli va ikkala

qismini 3 ga bo'lamiz: $95x \equiv 59 \pmod{308}$ Endi $\frac{308}{59}$ kasrni munosib kasrlarga yoyamiz.

$308 = 95 \cdot 3 + 23$; $95 = 23 \cdot 4 + 3$, $23 = 3 \cdot 7 + 2$, $3 = 2 \cdot 1 + 1$, $2 = 1 \cdot 2$. Demak,

$q_1 = 3$, $q_2 = 4$, $q_3 = 7$, $q_4 = 1$, $q_5 = 2$ bo'lib,

						1	2
						1	3
			3	7	07	08	

$P_{n-1} = P_4 = 107$ va $x \equiv (-1)^4 \cdot 107 \cdot 59 \pmod{308}$ yoki $x \equiv 153 \pmod{308}$.

Berilgan taqqoslamaning yechimlari $x \equiv 153, 461, 769 \pmod{924}$ dan iboratdir.

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